

A new genus and three new species of freshwater cochliopids (Caenogastropoda) from Goiás, Brazil

Un nuevo género y tres nuevas especies de cochliópodos de agua dulce (Caenogastropoda) de Goiás, Brasil

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ABSTRACT

Three new species of Cochliopidae collected in a warm spring in Central Brazil in Chapada dos Veadeiros, Goiás, are described, based on conchological and anatomical features. One of them belong to the new genus *Atomicus*, characterized by the minute size (less than 1 mm), discoid shell, and other anatomical features; the type species is *A. inopinatus* n. sp. The other two species belong to the genus *Heleobia*: *H. apua* and *H. pukua*. All new species are so far only found in the type locality. The conchological, anatomical exclusivities and differences are explored under the context of other Brazilian and South American rissooideans/truncatelloideans.

RESUMEN

Se describen tres nuevas especies de Cochliopidae recolectadas en una fuente cálida en el centro de Brasil, en Chapada dos Veadeiros, Goiás, con base en sus características anatómicas y conchológicas. Una de ellos pertenece al nuevo género *Atomicus*, caracterizado por su diminuto tamaño (menos de 1 mm), concha discooidal y otras características anatómicas; la especie tipo es *A. inopinatus* n. sp. Las otras dos especies pertenecen al género *Heleobia*: *H. apua* y *H. pukua*. Hasta ahora, todas las especies nuevas solo se encontraron en la localidad tipo. Las exclusividades y diferencias conchológicas, anatómicas se exploran en el contexto de otros rissooideos / truncatelloideos brasileños y sudamericanos.

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KEY WORDS: Brazil, fresh water gasteropoda, Cochliopidae, *Atomicus* new genus, genus *Heleobia*, new species.
PALABRAS CLAVE: Brasil, gasterópodos de agua dulce, Cochliopidae, *Atomicus* nuevo género, género *Heleobia*, nuevas especies.

INTRODUCTION

The non-marine truncatelloideans from the Brazilian territory are a constant source of new discoveries. Possibly

due to their low dispersion capacity and minute size, a high degree of endemicity is the rule (SIMONE, 2006b). In a recent

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Figures 1-3. Type locality images in Colinas do Sul, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Goiás, Brazil, 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W, three views at the time of collecting.

Figuras 1-3. Imágenes de la localidad tipo en Colinas do Sul, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Goiás, Brasil, 14° 13'19.41"S 47° 55'05.01"W, tres vistas en el momento del muestreo.

trip of the second author, some species of tiny freshwater snails were collected in a thermal spring in Goiás, central Brazil area (Figs. 2-3). This region belongs to the Cerrado biome, and is somewhat equidistant from Amazon Rainforest (north), Pantanal (the larger floodable area in the world – west), and Caatinga (semiarid environment – east). The collect region belongs to the Araguaia-Tocantins rivers basin, a pair of rivers which are the east extreme of the Amazon basin. Tocantins River mouth is together joint with that of Amazon river, almost directly into the Atlantic Ocean. The region is very understudied, and source of several novelties, as those presently introduced. The collect area is also close to the Chapada dos Veadeiros, a protected National Park with almost no malacological approach.

The Truncatelloidea encompass 27 families (WoRMS, 2020), occurring in all non-glacial regions, and in almost all biomes (SIMONE, 2006b). The family Cochliopidae includes 59 valid genera (WoRMS, 2020), but only three of them occur in South America (Simone, 2006a). The family is mostly defined molecularly (KOCH ET AL., 2015), and has a somewhat obscure morphological definition (Hershler, person. obs.), therefore, anatomical information is always important to be included. The detailed study of the morpho-anatomy of the samples collected in the above mentioned locality revealed three new enti-

ties, being two belonging to the complex genus *Heleobia* Stimpson, 1865 (type species *Paludina culminea* d'Orbigny, 1838, subsequent designation by Pilsbry, 1911) (HERSHLER & THOMPSON, 1992; KABAT & HERSHLER, 1993; KOCH ET AL, 2015), and the third belonging to a new genus. All taxa belong to the family Cochliopidae, subfamily Semisalsinae (KOCH ET AL., 2015).

With the continental Brazilian malacofauna inventoried (SIMONE, 2006a; BIRCKOLZ ET AL., 2016), including extra-Andean regions for the freshwater fauna, the detection of new taxa became relatively easy. The present paper is intended to provide a formal description for the three new species from Tocantins basin, in order to, based at least on their endemicity, provide a scientific basis for the protection of that environment and these species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens were hand collected after their visualization on the sediment (Fig. 1) and also by examining sediment samples under the stereomicroscope. They were conserved in 70% ETOH unanesthetized, and were studied by standard techniques (SIMONE, 2011), with the specimens dissected immersed in alcohol. The specimens were extracted from their shells by crushing the shell, all dissection steps were photographed and some structures were

processed for histological serial sections. All drawings were made with the aid of a camera lucida, the drawing pooling the average data of several specimens.

Anatomical abbreviations in the figures and in type lists:

aa, anterior aorta; af, afferent gill vessel; ag, albumen gland; an, anus; at, female atrium; au, auricle; bg, buccal ganglion; bm, buccal mass; br, subradular membrane; ce, cerebral ganglion; cg, capsule gland; cm, columellar muscle; cv, ctenidial vein; dc, dorsal chamber of buccal cavity; dd, duct to digestive gland; df, dorsal folds of buccal mass; dg, digestive gland; di, diaphragmatic septum; ef, esophageal folds; es, esophagus; ey, eye; fe, fecal pellets; fp, female pore; fs, foot sole; ft, foot; gi, gill; go, gonad; hg, hypo-branchial gland; ig, ingesting gland; in, intestine; jw, jaws; ki, kidney; m2-m10, odontophore muscles; mb, mantle border; mc, buccal circular muscle; mj, jaw and peribuccal muscles; mo, mouth; mt, mantle; oc, odontophore cartilage; od, odontophore; op, opercular pad; os, osphradium; ot, oral tube; ov, pallial oviduct; oy, ovary; pc, pericardium; pd,

penis duct; pe, penis; pg, anterior furrow of pedal glands; pl, pleural ganglion; pn, pedal ganglion; pt, prostate; ra, radula; rm, snout ventral retractor muscle; rn, radular nucleus; rs, radular sac; rt, rectum; sa, salivary gland aperture; sc, subradular cartilage; se, septum between esophageal origin and odontophore; sd, salivary duct; sg, salivary gland; sh, shell(s); sn, snout; spm, specimen(s); ss, style sac; st, stomach; su, subesophageal ganglion; sv, seminal vesicle; sy, statocyst; te, cephalic tentacle; tg, integument; ts, testis; ve, ventricle; vd, vas deferens; vo, visceral oviduct.

Abbreviation in listed material:

sh, shell(s); spm, specimen(s).

Institutional abbreviations:

MHNS: Museo de Historia Natural, Santiago de Compostela, Spain; MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain; MNHN: Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France; MNRI: Museu Nacional de Rio de Janeiro; MZSP: Museu de Zoologia da Universidade de São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil; NHMUK: National History Museum United Kingdom, London.

SYSTEMATICS

Family COCHLIOPIDAE

Subfamily SEMISALSINAE

Genus *Atomicus* new genus

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Type species: *Atomicus inopinatus* n. sp.

Etymology: The generic name is derived from the Greek tomikos, meaning cutting, precedes by prefix "a", a negative. The term means "not divisible", an allusion to the minute size.

Diagnosis: Shell discoid to turbini-form, umbilicus wide; minute (~1 mm). Peristome and operculum rounded. Peristome preceded by region detached from spire. Snout small; head-foot short, columellar muscle with both ends elevated. Gill wanting, but osphradium present. Radular teeth with multicuspid cutting edge. Odontophore with m5 muscle pair originated from cartilage.

Stomach posteriorly bilobed, style sac short. Intestine zigzagged both in visceral and pallial regions. Penis simple, lacking appendices, glands and papillae, relatively short; pallial vas deferens originated from anterior prostate end. Pallial oviduct with ingesting gland along terminal end of visceral oviduct; seminal receptacle multilobed.

List of included species: monotypic so far.

Atomicus inopinatus n. sp. (Figures 4-27)

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Type material. *Holotype*: BRAZIL • 1 spm (Figs. 4-5); Goiás, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Colinas do Sul; 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W; E. Rolán leg.; in a hot spring with a small river; MZSP 151666. *Paratypes*: BRAZIL • 30 spm; same data as for holotype; MZSP 97859 • 1 spm (Figs. 6-9); same data as for holotype; MZSP 151667 • 12 sh; same data as for holotype; MZSP 144658 • 1 sh (Fig. 11); same data as for holotype; MZSP 144656 • 1 sh (Fig. 12); same data as for holotype; MZSP 144662 • 1 sh (Fig. 13); same data as for holotype; MZSP 144657 • 1 sh (Fig. 14); same data as for holotype; MZSP 114654 • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; MNRJ • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; MNCN • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; MHNS • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; NHMUK.

Type locality: BRAZIL, Goiás, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Colinas do Sul, 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W, in a hot spring with a small river.

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin "*inopinata*", "not expected" alluding that this species was found several weeks after the collecting, in the sediments, having been overlooked because by its small size in the first examination *in situ*.

Description: Shell (Figs. 4-9, 11-14, 16, 17): Very small (up to 1 mm), discoid, almost planispiral; height/width ratio 0.7. General colour yellowish to pale beige (Figs. 6-9), translucent; some specimens (~30%) with additional brown coating, possibly sediment (Figs. 4-5). Spire scarcely elevate, ~30% of total height; of ~2.25 whorls (Figs. 5-7, 13-14). Protoconch (Figs. 9, 11, 16) almost one whorl, diameter of ~260 µm, nucleus of ~70 µm; surface smooth, not shiny (Figs. 16, 17). Teleoconch ~1.5 whorls, smooth, no sculpture except for prosocline growth lines (Figs. 11-14); region preceding aperture slightly detached from spire (Figs. 5, 7, 13, 14). Suture well marked, relatively deep (Figs. 16, 17). Aperture rounded (Figs. 5, 6, 13, 14), slightly prosocline (~20° with vertical axis) (Figs. 7, 8, 14), ~35% of total width, ~65% of total height; peristome continuous, very fine, with little contact or no contact with the previous whorl, normally clearly separate (Figs. 5, 6, 13, 14). Umbilicus wide, occupying ~25% of inferior area (Figs. 6, 8, 12).

Head-foot (Figs. 19, 22, 24): Relatively small, stubby, unpigmented. Foot thick, as wide as shell aperture, 1/4-1/2 larger than head. Eyes (ey) dark, located in the base of tentacles. Mesopodium (ft) thick, short, flanked dorsally by shallow lateral furrows. Anterior furrow of pedal glands (pg) deep, relatively short, restricted to anterior edge. Opercular

pad elliptic, terminal, occupying most of posterior foot dorsal surface. Pair of cephalic tentacles laterally positioned (te), each tentacle simple, thick, rather cylindrical ~same length as foot. Snout from ~80% (fig 19) to ~60% (Fig. 22) tentacles length (sn), ~twice tentacles' width; anterior end bilobed; mouth as transverse slit, ventral, central (mo). Columellar muscle (cm) thick, wide, ~3/4 whorl; right and left ends more elevated than medial region, right end ~twice as tall as left end. Haemocoel elliptical, on central region of head-foot (Fig. 24).

Operculum (Figs. 10, 15): Corneous, thin, translucent, yellow-beige, flexible, paucispiral. Outline elliptical-almost circular, occupying entire shell aperture (Fig. 6). Edges thin. Nucleus located in middle region of interior half, slightly displaced towards the inner side; from nucleus series of undulations correspondent to inner-superior growth edge. Inner surface glossy, scar rounded, occupying ~half of inner surface, located closer to internal edge, but not touching it.

Mantle organs (Figs. 23, 27): Somewhat wide, ~1 whorl in length. Mantle edge (mb) simple, thick; unpigmented. Osphradium short (os), softly curved (concavity left), simple; length ~10% pallial cavity length; located in anterior-left corner of cavity, close to mantle border. Gill wanting. Hypobranchial

Figures 4-18. *Atomiscus inopinatus* anatomical features. 4, 5: holotype MZSP 151666, apical and frontal views (W 0.98 mm); 6: paratype MZSP 151667, frontal view (W 0.98 mm); 7: same, left view; 8: same, umbilical view; 9: same, apical view; 10: operculum, direct illumination, outer view (W 0.28 mm); 11: paratype MZSP 144656, SEM, apical view (W 0.98 mm); 12: paratype MZSP 144662, SEM, umbilical view (W 0.98 mm); 13, 14: paratypes MZSP 144657, 144654 resp., SEM, frontal-slightly right views (W 0.81, 1.00 mm); 15: operculum, SEM, outer view (W 0.29 mm). 16: detail of apex, apical view; 17: same, detail of sculpture; 18: radula, SEM, general view.

Figuras 4-18. Características anatómicas de Atomiscus inopinatus. 4, 5: holotipo MZSP 151666, vistas apical y frontal (W 0,98 mm); 6: paratipo MZSP 151667, vista frontal (ancho 0,98 mm); 7: el mismo, vista izquierda; 8: el mismo, vista umbilical; 9: el mismo, vista apical; 10: opérculo, iluminación directa, vista externa (0,28 mm ancho); 11: paratipo MZSP 144656, MEB, vista apical (ancho 0,98 mm); 12: paratipo MZSP 144662, MEB, vista umbilical (W 0,98 mm); 13, 14: paratipos MZSP 144657, 144654 resp., MEB, vistas frontales ligeramente desde derecha (W 0,81, 1,00 mm); 15: opérculo, MEB, vista externa (W 0,29 mm); 16: detalle del ápice, MEB, vista apical; 17: mismo ejemplar, detalle de escultura; 18: rádula, MEB, vista general.

gland inconspicuous. Rectum wide, with strong zigzagged loop; bearing aligned series of elliptical fecal pellets (fe), easily seen by transparency. Anus

simple, sessile (Fig. 27: an) to shortly siphoned (Fig. 23), located close to mantle border. Genital structures relatively massive, described below.

Visceral mass (Fig. 23): Length ~2.5 whorls. Most structures pale beige to white in colour. Stomach (st) as anterior structure, compressing ventrally small reno-pericardial structures (pc, ki); stomach of ~0.5 whorl and with almost entire adjacent whorl width. Digestive gland (dg) of ~1.5 whorls, mostly posterior and right to stomach. Gonad (oy) running along columellar surface of each whorl when mature, weakly distinct from digestive gland.

Circulatory and excretory systems (Figs. 23, 27): Pericardium narrow, located longitudinally between stomach and pallial cavity (pc), volume ~1/20 of that of visceral mass; auricle (au) anterior, just posterior to posterior end of ctenidial vein (cv) detectable running along left-posterior edge; ventricle (ve) posterior, simple. Kidney (ki) minute, slightly smaller than pericardium, located in right side of pallial cavity posterior end; inner tissue totally solid, white. Nephrostome small, transverse, close to pericardium.

Digestive system (Figs. 20-21, 24, 26-27): Mouth as slit in antero-ventral end of snout (Fig. 24: mo). Buccal mass bulged, occupying entire snout inner surface and ~1/3 of haemocoelic volume (Fig. 24: od). Pair of jaw plates (Fig. 20: jw) somewhat separated from each other; each jaw oval, thin, translucent. Odontophore spherical, with ~half of buccal mass volume (Fig. 20: od). Odontophore muscles (Figs. 20, 26): mj, pair of jaw and peribuccal muscles, and odontophore protractors, originating in lateral and ventral region of mouth, running towards posterior as part of oral tube along ~half odontophore length (Fig. 20), inserte in latero-ventral mid region of odontophore cartilages, more distinct in lateral region; m2, pair of posterior retractor muscles of odontophore (Fig. 20), narrow, originating in lateral region of haemocoel inner surface, in its middle level, running towards anterior distance equivalent to buccal mass length, inserted in postero-lateral region of odontophore; m4, pair of main dorsal tensor muscle of radula (Fig. 26), broad, thick, surrounding outer lateral surface of

odontophore cartilages, originating from their ventro-lateral surface; m5, pair of secondary dorsal tensor muscles of radula (Fig. 26), narrow and thick, originating in posterior edge of odontophore cartilages, running towards medial and anterior; m6, horizontal muscle, thin, wide, connecting ventral edge of both odontophore cartilages along ~80% of their length (Fig. 26). Odontophore cartilages elliptic, somewhat thick and flattened laterally (Fig. 26: oc). Radular sac with length ~twice that of odontophore (Fig. 20: rs); radular nucleus (rn) slightly broader. Radula (Fig. 18): rachidian occupying ~1/5 of radular width, cutting edge with more prominent central cusp, 5-7 pairs of secondary cusps gradually becoming smaller towards lateral; anterior edge strongly concave, ~70% of posterior-basal edge; pair of basal cusps as long as central cusp, located in middle region of pair of strong concavities. Lateral teeth as wide as rachidian; ~12 cusps on their cutting-lateral border; middle cusps larger, with central cusps larger than that of rachidian. Inner marginal teeth spoon-like, base narrow ~half of rachidian; ~33-35 rather uniform small cusps in lateral-terminal edge. Outer lateral teeth similar to inner ones, as long as, but with ~half their width; cusps preceding both sides of terminal end; internal edge with 5-6 decreasing cusps; outer edge with ~ 18 small, slightly uniform cusps.

Pair of salivary glands small (Fig. 24: sg), white, with length equivalent to buccal mass length, ~3 times longer than wide. Esophagus slightly sinuous (Figs. 20, 24: es), with no detectable glandular region (Figs. 23, 27). Stomach dimensions and positions above described (visceral mass); possessing main gastric chamber posterior, with rather bilobed posterior surface, each lobe separated by duct to digestive gland (dd); style sac marked by gradual narrowing (Figs. 27: ss), length equivalent to remaining gastric length. Style sac totally separated from intestine; esophagus inserted just ventrally to style sac and intestinal origins, on middle-ventral stomach side (Fig. 27); duct to digestive gland as wide

Figures 19-27. *Atomicus inopinatus* anatomical features. 19: head-foot, female, frontal view; 20: foregut, right-slightly ventral view, jaw plate seen by transparency; 21: central nervous system, ventral view; 22: head-foot, male, frontal view, adjacent region of prostate also shown as in situ and slightly deflected to the right (left in Fig.); 23: pallial cavity roof, female, ventral-inner view, and uncoiled visceral mass; 24: head and haemocoel, ventral view, foot and columellar muscle removed; 25: pallial oviduct, ventral view; 26: odontophore, dorsal view, outer layer of muscles and membranes removed, left structures (right in Fig.) deflected, right ones as in situ; 27: mid and hindgut, and pericardium, ventral view, topology of mantle border also shown.

Figuras 19-27. Características anatómicas de Atomicus inopinatus. 19: cabeza-pie, hembra, vista frontal; 20: intestino anterior, vista ventral ligeramente derecha, placa de la mandíbula vista por transparencia; 21: sistema nervioso central, vista ventral; 22: cabeza-pie, macho, vista frontal, mostrando también la región adyacente a la próstata como in situ y ligeramente desviada hacia la derecha (izquierda en la Fig.); 23: techo de la cavidad paleal, hembra, vista ventral-interna y masa visceral desenrollada; 24: cabeza y hemocelo, vista ventral, retirados el pie y músculo columelar; 25: oviducto paleal, vista ventral; 26: odontóforo, vista dorsal, retiradas la capa externa de músculos y membranas, estructuras izquierdas (derecha en Fig.) desviadas, derechas como in situ; 27: intestino medio y posterior, y pericardio, vista ventral, también se muestra la topología del borde del manto.

as posterior esophagus (Fig. 27: dd), running towards posterior. Intestine originating dorsally and to the left of esophageal insertion (Fig. 27: in), as wide as local esophagus; three closely set intestinal loops, similar in size, first loop ventral, second loop dorsal-right from style sac. Third loop pallial as rectum (Figs. 23, 27: rt). Rectum fecal pellets and anus described above (pallial cavity).

Genital system, male (Fig. 22): *Vas deferens* relatively straight in gastric and renal region, inserted terminally in prostate (vd). Prostate (pt) with $\sim 1/6$ width of pallial cavity, $\sim 1/3$ its length, white, totally closed (tubular). Pallial vas deferens originating by tapering prostate anterior region (inferior vd); in short distance penetrating in floor of pallial cavity by side of penis base, running immersed in integument. Penis (pe), simple, stubby, curved, base broad, gradually tapering to bluntly pointed tip; length $\sim 1/4$ total head-foot length and width. Penis duct seen by transparency along central penial region, up to penis distal tip; aperture distal, simple, small.

Genital system, female (Figs. 23, 25): Ovary (oy) subterminal in last visceral whorl, $\sim 1/5$ size of digestive gland. Visceral oviduct very narrow, running along middle level of columellar surface of visceral mass ~ 1 whorl long (vo). Oviduct insertion lateral in tip of elongated ingesting gland (ig), gradually tapering towards anterior, inserted between middle and anterior thirds of pallial

oviduct gland. Seminal vesicle (sv) flattened, trifid posterior end, narrowing rather subtly; inserted to the right and slightly anterior to insertion of ingesting gland. Capsule gland with anterior third narrower than posterior $2/3$, ending in very short hollow atrium (at). Female pore as small, protruded papilla (fp).

Central nervous system (Fig. 21): Nerve ring located just posterior to buccal mass (Fig. 24: ce). Each cerebral ganglion (ce) greatly fused with pleural ganglia (pl), both forming somewhat oval mass, with size equivalent to esophageal section; cerebral commissure narrow, with \sim half length of each ganglion. Pleural ganglia (pl) of difficult individualization, with \sim half size of cerebral ganglia, located just ventral to them. Each pedal ganglion (pn) as large as cerebral ganglion, somewhat spherical; pedal commissure as long as cerebral commissure. Pair of statocysts (sy) located in ventro-posterior side of pedal ganglia; with large, single statolith inside.

Measurements (width and height in mm): Usually between 0.7-0.9 mm in width (N= 30). Holotype MZSP 151666 (Figs. 1-2): 0.98 by 0.55; Paratype MZSP 151667 (Figs. 6-9): 0.98 by 0.66;

Distribution: Only known in the type locality.

Habitat: Found under leaves of a small river (Fig. 1) which continues the warm spring (Figs 2, 3), sandy-mud bottom, ~ 0.5 m deep, slow water flow. Presence of anthropogenic impact.

Remarks: See Discussion.

Genus *Heleobia* Simpson, 1865

Heleobia apua n. sp. (Figures 28-53)

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Type material. *Holotype:* BRAZIL • 1 spm (Fig. 29); Goiás, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Colinas do Sul; 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W; E. Rolán leg.; in a hot spring with a small river; MZSP 144664. *Paratypes:* BRAZIL • same data as for holotype; MZSP 27863 • 6 sh; same data as for holotype; MZSP 144665 • 30 spm; same data as for holotype; MZSP 97861 • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; MNRJ • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; MNCN • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; MHNS • 2 spm; same data as for holotype; NHMUK.

Type locality: BRAZIL, Goiás, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Colinas do Sul, 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W, in a hot spring with a small river.

Etymology: The specific name is a Latinization from the Guarani language, the word *apua*, meaning rounded, and allusion to the shell's outline.

Figures 28-38. *Heleobia apua* anatomical features. 28: paratype MZSP 97861, frontal view (L 3.86 mm); 29: holotype MZSP 144664, SEM, frontal view (L 3.60 mm); 30: paratype MZSP 144665 right view (L 3.75 mm); 31: same detail of apex, apical view; 32, 33: operculum of figure 28, outer and inner views (W 1.27 mm); 34, 35: paratype MZSP 97861 operculum, SEM, outer and inner views (W 1.37 mm); 36: detail of operculum surface; 37, 38: radula, SEM.

Figuras 28-38. Características anatómicas de Heleobia apua. 28: paratipo MZSP 97861, vista frontal (L 3,86 mm); 29: holotipo MZSP 144664, MEB, vista frontal (L 3,60 mm); 30: paratipo MZSP 144665 vista derecha (L 3,75 mm); 31: mismo detalle de ápice, vista apical; 32, 33: opérculo de la figura 28, vistas externa e interna (ancho 1,27 mm); 34, 35: paratipo MZSP 97861 opérculo, MEB, vistas externa e interna (W 1,37 mm); 36: detalle de la superficie del opérculo; 37, 38: rádula, MEB.

Diagnosis: shell shorter than 4 mm; suture shallow, whorls profile convex, tip slightly pointed; wide complete peristome; umbilicus lacking. Operculum simple, reticulated. Penis long, thick, lacking appendices. Receptacle bifid; ingesting gland zigzagging. Freshwater.

Description: Shell (Figs. 28-31): size up to 4 mm; elongate, ovate to cone-shaped, with slightly curved profile, not umbilicate; whorls slightly convex, shallow suture, adult ~4-5 whorls. Sculpture absent except for growth lines, and some obsolete, sparse spiral striae (Figs. 29, 31). Colour pale brown, translucent (Fig. 28). Protoconch (Fig. 31) of ~250 μ m, with ~1.5 smooth whorls. Teleoconch of ~3.5 whorls. Spire angle ~45°. Aperture semi-circular, peristome continuous; ~40% of total shell length, ~65% of shell width; profile orthocone (Fig. 30); inner lip almost straight, ~50° in relation to longitudinal axis; outer lip and inner third of inner lip forming continuous semi-circle (Figs. 28, 29), relatively thick; anal region with relatively narrow notch, with small callus on left edge; incumbent region widely rounded. Umbilicus closed.

Head-foot (Figs. 41, 42, 44, 50): Relatively wide, stubby; exposed areas pigmented dark brown, almost black, except for lighter region in peri-buccal region of snout. Mesopodium thick, relatively short (Fig. 41: fs). Anterior furrow of pedal glands (Fig. 41: pg) deep, restricted to anterior edge. Opercular pad (Fig. 41: op) elliptic, subterminal, occupying most of posterior foot dorsal surface. Head bulbous, with ~90% of foot width; pair of cephalic tentacles (te) simple, thick, with ~half foot length. Eye (ey) at outer side of tentacles base; ~half width of tentacles base. Snout slightly shorter than tentacles length; ~1/4 tentacles width (sn); anterior end rounded dorsally, notched ventrally (Fig. 44); mouth triangular, subterminal, ventral (Figs. 44: mo). Columellar muscle thick, ~3/4 whorl, simply curving to right (Figs. 41, 41: cm). Haemocoel elongated, in central region of head-foot (Fig. 44).

Operculum (Figs. 32-35): Corneous, thin, translucent, pale yellow-beige, flexible, paucispiral. Outline semi-circu-

lar, ~twice as long as wide, occupying partially shell aperture (Fig. 28). Edges relatively thick. Nucleus located in middle region of inner third, (Figs. 32, 34); after nucleus, only sub-parallel growth lines and microscopic mosaic of reticulate striae (Fig. 36). Inner surface glossy, scar elliptic, ~3 times longer than wide, occupying ~half of inner surface, located closer to internal edge, but not touching it (Figs. 33, 35).

Mantle organs (Figs. 39, 40, 45): Somewhat narrow, with ~1 whorl in length. Mantle edge simple, not very thick, wide, unpigmented. Osphradium short (os), elliptical, simple; length ~6% pallial cavity length, located in anterior-left corner of cavity, close to gill, away from mantle border. Gill (gi) elongated, narrow, with ~80% of pallial cavity length and 25% of cavity width; anterior end bluntly pointed, posterior to mantle edge; posterior region narrowing gradually, filaments ending at some distance from pericardium. Gill filaments rather triangular, distal tip rounded (Fig. 45: gi). Between gill and rectum, a short distance equivalent to 5% of pallial cavity width. Hypobranchial gland (hg) thin. Rectum wide, relatively straight, reaching up to 1/3 of pallial cavity width in some points; bearing aligned series of rounded fecal pellets (fe), easily seen by transparency (Figs. 39, 40, 51); rectum displaced from right mantle cavity edge by pallial genital ducts. Anus simple, shortly siphoned, located a distance from mantle edge ~5% of cavity length. Genital ducts running along right edge, relatively massive, described below.

Visceral mass (Figs. 39, 40, 43, 51): Length ~3 whorls, leaving ~2 first shell whorls empty in adult specimens. Most structures pale beige to white in colour, mantle locally pigmented dark brown. Stomach as anterior structure, compressing ventrally small reno-pericardial structures; stomach of ~0.5 whorl, with width almost as entire adjacent whorl. Digestive gland greenish, of ~2.5 whorls, mostly posterior to stomach. Gonad running along columellar surface of each whorl when mature, weakly distinct from digestive gland. Other genital and digestive details below.

Figures 39-45. *Heleobia apua* anatomical features. 39: pallial cavity roof, female, ventral-inner view, and coiled visceral mass; 40: same for male, pallial vas deferens detached from integument and shown as in situ; 41: head-foot, male, ventro-right view; 42: same, frontal view; 43: detail of first whorl of visceral mass slightly uncoiled, female, apical view; 44: head and haemocoel, ventral view, foot and columellar muscle removed; 45: pallial cavity roof, female, transverse section along its middle region.

Figuras 39-45. Características anatómicas de Heleobia apua. 39: techo de la cavidad paleal, hembra, vista ventral-interna y masa visceral enrollada; 40: lo mismo para macho, los conductos deferentes paleales desprendidos del tegumento y mostrados como in situ; 41: cabeza-pie, macho, vista ventral-derecha; 42: lo mismo, vista frontal; 43: detalle de la primera vuelta de masa visceral ligeramente desenrollada, vista apical, hembra; 44: cabeza y hemocelo, vista ventral, pie y músculo columelar extraídos; 45: techo de la cavidad paleal, hembra, sección transversal a lo largo de su región media.

Circulatory and excretory systems (Fig. 39): Pericardium narrow, located longitudinally between stomach and pallial cavity (pc), volume $\sim 1/10$ of that of visceral mass; auricle (au) anterior, small, just posterior to posterior end of ctenidial vein (cv); ventricle (ve) posterior, simple. Kidney (ki) minute, slightly smaller than pericardium, located in right side of pallial cavity posterior end; inner tissue totally solid, white. Nephrostome small, transverse, located close to pericardium.

Digestive system (Figs. 46-49, 51): Mouth at antero-ventral end of snout (Fig. 44: mo). Pair of strong ventral retractor muscles of snout and mouth (Figs. 44, 53: rm); originating in middle level of haemocoelic ventral floor; running close to median line towards anterior, flanking ventral surface of buccal mass, passing through nerve ring (Fig. 53); inserted along ventral wall of snout. Buccal mass occupying entire inner surface of snout and $\sim 1/4$ of haemocoelic volume. Pair of jaw plates (Fig. 47: jw) close to each other, restricted to dorsal wall of buccal cavity; each jaw oval and very thin, translucent. Odontophore spherical, with \sim half of buccal mass volume. Odontophore muscles (Figs. 48, 49): mj, pair of jaw and peribuccal muscles, originating in lateral and ventral region of mouth, running towards posterior as part of oral tube along \sim half odontophore length (Fig. 46), inserted in latero-ventral mid region of odontophore cartilages (Fig. 48), united in median region; m11, pair of thin retractor jugal muscle, originating in middle part of haemocoel floor, running anteriorly along \sim half odontophore length, inserted on lateral branch of mj (Fig. 46); m2, pair of posterior retractor muscles of odontophore (Figs. 46, 48), narrow, originating in lateral region of haemocoel inner surface, in its middle level, running towards anterior for a distance slightly longer than buccal mass length, inserted in postero-lateral region of odontophore cartilages (Fig. 46); m4, pair of main dorsal tensor muscle of radula (Fig. 49), broad and thick, surrounding outer lateral surface of odontophore cartilages, originating from their ventro-lateral surface,

inserted in lateral edges of subradular cartilage in its region in buccal cavity, and also in radular sac region preceding buccal cavity; m5, pair of secondary dorsal tensor muscles of radula (Figs. 48, 49), narrow and thick, originating in posterior surface of m4, running towards medial and anterior, between cartilages, inserted in ventral side of radular ribbon in its region exposed in buccal cavity (Fig. 49); m6, horizontal muscle, thin and wide, connecting ventral edge of both odontophore cartilages along $\sim 75\%$ of their length (Fig. 49); m10, pair of ventral protractor muscles of buccal mass (Fig. 46), relatively narrow and thin, originating in ventral edge of mouth, just ventral to retractor muscle (mr) origin, running towards posterior for a distance equivalent to odontophore length, inserted in posterior-ventral edge of odontophore cartilages; mc, layer of transversal muscles in ventral region of buccal mass, covered by m10 pair (Figs. 46, 47). Subradular cartilage relatively wide in region of buccal cavity (Fig. 48: sc). Odontophore cartilages elliptic, somewhat flattened laterally, \sim twice as long as wide, anterior and posterior edges rounded and similar (Fig. 49: oc). Radular sac with length ~ 1.5 times that of odontophore (Fig. 46: rs); radular nucleus (rn) not widening. Radula (Figs. 37-38): rachidian tooth triangular, distal tip curved inwards, with $\sim 25\%$ of radular ribbon width, height about $3/4$ of width, base simple, weakly arched, 2 pairs of latero-basal cusps; 5 terminal triangular cusps, central cusp more than twice as large as others, cusps greatly diminishing towards lateral; cusps restricted to distal, curved edge; lateral tooth with main region rectangular, with \sim twice rachidian height and its same width, $\sim 5-6$ cusps similar to those of rachidian, cusps smaller in both ends, being gradually larger towards median, slightly lateral region; inner and outer lateral tooth of similar shape, the outer tooth $\sim 30\%$ narrower than inner marginal tooth, \sim twice the length of lateral tooth and $\sim 40\%$ narrower, general form as a rod curved inwards at tip, tip flattened, bearing ~ 10 inner terminal cusps of similar size; each cusp small, sharply pointed.

Figures 46-53. *Heleobia apua* anatomical features. 46: foregut, left view; 47: buccal cavity and anterior esophagus, both opened longitudinally, odontophore removed, salivary duct (sd) seen by translucency; 48: odontophore, ventral view, first layer of muscles and membranes removed; 49: odontophore, dorsal view, radular sac removed, both cartilages (oc) deflected; 50: isolated head, male, dorsal view; 51: mid and hindgut, ventral view, topology of some adjacent structures shown; 52: pallial oviduct, ventral view, topology of anus shown; 53: central nervous system, ventral view, adjacent retractor muscle of snout (rm) shown.

Figuras 46-53. Características anatómicas de Heleobia apua. 46: *digestivo anterior, vista izquierda;* 47: *cavidad bucal y esófago anterior, ambos cortados longitudinalmente, odontóforo retirado, conducto salival (sd) visto por transparencia;* 48: *odontóforo, vista ventral, primera capa de músculos y membranas retiradas;* 49: *odontóforo, vista dorsal, saco radular retirado, ambos cartilagos (oc) desviados;* 50: *cabeza aislada, macho, vista dorsal;* 51: *intestino medio y posterior, vista ventral, se muestra la topología de algunas estructuras adyacentes;* 52: *oviducto paleal, vista ventral, se muestra la topología del ano;* 53: *sistema nervioso central, vista ventral, se muestra el músculo retractor adyacente del morro (rm).*

Salivary gland small (Figs. 44: sg), white, with maximum length ~half buccal mass length; salivary aperture (Fig. 41: sa) in middle level of the inner edge of dorsal fold, preceded by short portion of salivary ducts (sd) running immersed in them. Dorsal folds of buccal mass (Fig. 47: df) smooth, simple, wide, located close to each other, originated from jaw plates, fainting in esophageal origin. Esophagus simple along haemocoel (Figs. 23-24: es), almost straight, lacking glandular areas (Figs. 46, 47); esophageal inner surface simple, low, weak longitudinal folds. Stomach dimensions and positions described above (visceral mass); possessing main gastric chamber posterior, with rounded posterior surface, and narrow style sac (Figs. 51: ss), style sac length ~half remaining gastric length. Style sac totally separated from intestine; esophagus (es) inserted just posterior to style sac and intestine (in), on left stomach side; duct to digestive gland ~half of posterior esophagus width, originating at a short distance posterior to esophageal insertion (Fig. 51: dd), running towards posterior. Intestine originating anterior to esophageal insertion (Figs. 51: in), with ~twice esophagus width, and left of style sac; running surrounding ventrally-anteriorly the style sac up to dorsal region of kidney, subtly curving in region preceding pallial cavity. Rectum fecal pellets and anus described above (pallial cavity). Fecal pellets formed only after renal portion of intestine (Figs. 51: fe).

Genital system, male (Figs. 40, 42, 50): Testis (ts) restricted to posterior half of digestive gland (Figs. 40: ts). Seminal vesicle (sv) very convolute, located in columellar region of visceral mass ventral to stomach, colour pale grey-iridescent; inserted in prostate subterminally (Fig. 40: sv), just posterior to middle level of prostate. Prostate with ~1/4 pallial cavity width, somewhat dorso-ventrally flattened, white (Fig. 40: pt). Vas deferens originating from prostate ventral-middle region, relatively close to visceral vas deferens insertion (Fig. 40: vd); after long dis-

tance penetrating in floor of pallial cavity up to penis base, running immersed in integument (Fig. 50: vd). Penis (Figs. 42, 50: pe), simple, curved, elongated (almost as long as pallial cavity) base slightly broad, slightly and gradually tapering up to rounded tip. Penis duct seen by transparency, running straight along central penial region, up to penis distal tip (Fig. 50: pd); aperture distal, simple, small.

Genital system, female (Figs. 39, 43, 45, 52): Visceral structures similar to those of males; ovary (Fig. 43: oy) possessing 3-4 relatively distant bundles. Visceral oviduct very narrow, running along middle level of columellar surface of visceral mass ~1 whorl (vo). Visceral oviduct inserted subterminally in posterior-left region of pallial oviduct (Fig. 52: vo). In this region, seminal receptacle projected anteriorly, and ingesting gland projected posteriorly. Seminal receptacle bilobed distally, size ~1/30 of pallial oviduct (sr). Ingesting gland similar in size to receptacle, looking like tubular zigzag (ig). Albumen gland (ag) and capsule gland (cg) about half and half along oviduct length; walls thick glandular, white, lumen flattened (Fig. 45); minute terminal atrium with walls not very thick, tapering up to small female pore. Female pore shortly siphoned, papilla-like, turned anteriorly (fp), located close to and to the right of anus.

Central nervous system (Fig. 53): Nerve ring located just posterior to buccal mass, with pedal ganglia slightly more anterior (Fig. 44: pn) than remaining ganglia. Each cerebral ganglion (ce) oval, with size equivalent to esophageal section; cerebral commissure narrow, about as long as each ganglion. Pleural ganglia (pl) with ~half size of cerebral ganglia, located just ventral to them widely fused with cerebral ganglia. Each pedal ganglion (pn) slightly larger than cerebral ganglion, somewhat spherical, pedal commissure ~half of each ganglion length. Cerebro-pedal and pleuro-pedal connectives about as long as pedal ganglia. Subesophageal ganglion (su) with ~half pleural ganglion size, located a short distance from

right pleural ganglion. Pair of statocysts (sy) located in ventro-posterior side of pedal ganglia; left one slightly more distant than right statocyst.

Measurements (length and width in mm): The largest specimens reach up to 4 mm. Holotype 3.60 by 1.88; paratype MZSP 97861 (Fig. 28): 3.86 by 1.90.

Distribution: Only known in the type locality.

Habitat: Found under leaves in the water course of a small river (Fig. 1) which continues the warm spring (Figs 2, 3), sandy-mud bottom, ~0.5 m deep, slow water flow. Presence of anthropogenic impact.

Heleobia pukua n. sp. (Figures 54-66)

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Type material. Holotype: BRAZIL • 1 spm (Fig. 57); Goiás, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Colinas do Sul, 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W; E. Rolán leg.; in a hot spring with a small river; MZSP 151668. **Paratypes:** BRAZIL • 19 spm (Figs. 54-56); same data as for holotype; MZSP 97863 • 3 sh; MZSP 144666.

Type locality: BRAZIL, Goiás, Chapada dos Veadeiros, Colinas do Sul, 14°13'19.41"S 47°55'05.01"W.

Etymology: The specific name is a Latinization from the Guarani language, the word *puku*, meaning elongated, long, an allusion to the shell's outline.

Diagnosis: shell shorter than 4 mm; suture shallow, whorls profile straight, tip slightly pointed; wide incomplete peristome; umbilicus lacking. Operculum double-layered, only with growth lines. Penis long, narrow, lacking appendices. Receptacle balloon-like; ingesting gland with single loop. Freshwater.

Distinctive description: **Shell** (Figs. 54-59): elongate, conical, with somewhat straight profile; whorls weakly convex, shallow suture, adult ~5-6 whorls. Sculpture absent except for growth lines. Colour pale brown, translucent (Figs. 54-56). Protoconch (Figs. 58-59) of ~340 µm with ~1 smooth whorl, mostly eroded in adult forms. Teleoconch of ~6 whorls. Spire angle ~35°. Aperture semi-circular, peristome interrupted in superior columellar area; ~35% of total shell length, ~70 of shell width; profile ortho-cline (Fig. 55); inner lip weakly concave, ~40° in relation to longitudinal axis; outer lip and interior third on inner lip forming continuous semi-circle (Figs. 54, 57), relatively thick; anal region lacking notch, only angle of ~85°; incurrent region widely rounded, slightly projected anteriorly. Callus very thin. Umbilicus closed.

Head-foot and operculum (Figs. 62, 63): Characters similar to *H. apua*, except

for: head slightly wider; anterior region of snout flatter, with mouth (mo) in middle of pair of convexities; colour brown in exposed areas, with white band just above anterior surface of snout (Fig. 54 by translucency). Operculum more rounded by ~10%; inner scar also more rounded, mainly in middle; operculum with two layers, separated from each other in middle and superior regions (Fig. 66).

Mantle organs (Figs. 61, 65): Features similar to *H. apua*, distinctions following: osphradium (os) slightly ~20% larger and longer; gill (gi) filaments ~20% taller; intestine (in) slightly more zigzagging in pallial hoof.

Visceral mass (Fig. 61): As that of *H. apua*, except for one more whorl in length.

Circulatory and excretory systems (Fig. 61): Similar to those of *H. apua*, except in being ~10% smaller.

Digestive system (Figs. 61, 62): Most attributes similar to those of *H. apua*, distinctions and remarkable characters following: buccal mass (bm) and odontophore with same components, ~30% larger, with esophageal pair of folds slightly longer and taller. Radula (Fig. 60) with similar components and proportions; rachidian with 7 more uniform and smaller distal cusps, 4 pairs of basal

Figures 54-60. *Heleobia pukua* anatomical features. 54-56: paratype MZSP 97863 (L 4.39 mm), frontal, right and dorsal views; 57: holotype, SEM (L 4.28 mm); 58: paratype MZSP 97863, detail of protoconch, SEM, apical view; 59: same for paratype 144666; 60: radula, SEM.

Figuras 54-60. Características anatómicas de Heleobia pukua. 54-56: paratipo MZSP 97863 (L 4,39 mm), vistas frontal, derecha y dorsal; 57: holotipo, MEB (L 4,28 mm); 58: paratipo MZSP 97863, detalle de la protoconcha, MEB, vista apical; 59: lo mismo para el paratipo 144666; 60: rádula, MEB.

cusps more uniform and proportionally smaller; lateral and marginal teeth with proportionally smaller and more uniform distal cusps. Esophagus slightly longer, stored in zigzag fashion in haemocoel (Fig. 62: es). Salivary glands absent. Stomach (st) with

pointed projection in right side of its main portion; style sac (ss) and intestine (in) slightly broader; intestine with ~20% larger fecal pellets (pe) and more zigzagging in pallial roof.

Genital system, male (Figs. 63, 64): Most characters similar to those of *H.*

Figures 61-65. *Heleobia pukua* anatomical features. 61: pallial cavity roof, male, ventral-inner view, and visceral mass, prostate slightly deflected; 62: head and haemocoel, ventral view, foot and columellar muscle removed; 63: head-foot, male, frontal view; 64: detail of penis region, dorsal view; 65: pallial oviduct, ventral view, topology of some adjacent structures also shown.

Figuras 61-65. Características anatómicas de Heleobia pukua. 61: techo de la cavidad paleal, macho, vista ventral-interna y masa visceral, próstata ligeramente desviada; 62: cabeza y hemocele, vista ventral, pie y músculo columelar retirados; 63: cabeza-pie, macho, vista frontal; 64: detalle de la región del pene, vista dorsal; 65: oviducto paleal, vista ventral, también se muestra la topología de algunas estructuras adyacentes.

apua, except for: Seminal vesicle (sv) coiling in smaller area, coiling apparently more chaotic. Separation between visceral and pallial vas deferens (vd) in prostate (pt) ~60% further away. Penis (pe) narrower, slender, ~50% longer,

profile more uniform; colour pure white.

Genital system, female (Fig. 65): Visceral and pallial structures mostly like those of *H. apua*, with main differences in posterior region of pallial oviduct:

Figure 66. *Heleobia pukua* operculum in light microscopy in three positions from inner view (left) to profile (right), showing double layers (W 1.2 mm).

Figura 66. Opérculo de Heleobia pukua en microscopía óptica en tres posiciones desde vista interna (izquierda) hasta perfil (derecha), mostrando capas dobles (W 1,2 mm).

visceral oviduct (vo) inserted in base of ingesting gland (ig), containing single wide loop inside; seminal receptacle (sr) simple, balloon-like. Separation between albumen (ag) and capsule (cg) glands slightly wider. Female atrium (at) ~3 times longer and wider.

Central nervous system (Fig. 62): With same features as those of *H. apua*, except for subesophageal ganglion (su) being less sharp and located slightly further away.

DISCUSSION

As stated elsewhere (SIMONE, 2006b, 2011), what is now referred as Rissoidea Truncatelloidea and Littori-

Measurements (length and width in mm): Holotype: MZSP 151668: 4.28 by 1.76. Paratype MZSP 97863 (Figs. 54-56): 4.39 by 1.99.

Distribution: Only known in the type locality.

Habitat: Found under leaves in the water course of a small river (Fig. 1) which continues the warm spring (Figs 2, 3), sandy-mud bottom, ~0.5 m deep, slow water flow. Presence of anthropogenic impact.

Remarks: see Discussion.

noidea are part of a single taxon supported by several interesting synapomorphies, such as the closure of the

male and female genital ducts. They can be regarded as forming a single superfamily within Caenogastropoda, or as three superfamilies united in a suborder within that order. This taxonomical treatment is still in a state of flux, as the group is highly diverse. This is the reason for calling "rissooideans/truncatelloidean" in present paper.

The new genus *Atomicus* is the first discoid Rissooidea/Truncatelloidea taxon found in Brazilian territory, and possibly in South America as far as known. That, beforehand, makes easy its distinction with other local genera. Additionally, with less than 1 mm, it appears to be the smallest freshwater taxon in the mainland. The fully developed genital structures and gonads with developed gametes show that the examined specimens are adult. Anatomically, on the other hand, *Atomicus* looks similar to the local cochliopids, such as the *Heleobia* described herein. The main difference is in the absence of the gill, which can be explained by the minuteness of the species. However, the osphradium remained (Fig. 23: os), its size is proportional to the osphradia of the other genera. The overall anatomical attributes also look like the taxa of the same family, including the size, position and form of digestive tubes and genital structures. Because of the small size, most structures look simplified. As main differences of the new genus, the following can be evoked: the foot is proportionally shorter (Figs. 19, 22); the odontophore pair m5 originated directly from the cartilages (Fig. 26); the central radular tooth (rachidian and lateral) has minute, more numerous and more uniform cusps (Fig. 18); prostate has its connection with vas deferens at both extremities (Fig. 22: pt) (they are not subterminal); and the central nervous system lacks the bulged region of pedal nerves (Fig. 21). The female pallial oviduct has a somewhat similar arrangement as in *Heleobia*, with an ingesting gland in the end of visceral oviduct and a receptacle originating close to it (Fig. 25). This feature justifies the familiar placement. The simplified

inner gastric surface, lacking sorting areas, distinguishes *Atomicus* from several north hemisphere genera, e.g., *Hydrobia* Hartmann, 1821 and *Spurwinkia* Davis, Mazurkiewicz & Mandrachia, 1982 (DAVIS ET AL, 1982).

Both *Heleobia* species described herein are apparently small species for the genus. They rarely reach 4 mm, while the other species are easily larger than 6-7 mm (SIMONE, 2006a, as *Littoridina*). Two species are still smaller, such as *H. inconspicua* (HAAS, 1938), from the Brazilian northeast, and *H. pusilla* (Haas, 1949), from the Amazon region, from which both species described herein differ in having a more pointed spire and protoconch; from the former both still differ in having a proportionally larger aperture; and from the latter in having less convex whorls and a sharper profile. *Heleobia apua* and *H. pukua* are sympatric and similar in shell attributes. Most of the distinctive features between both species are explored above. This discussion is mostly based on what appears to be the more important features. The shells can be distinguished from each other by the following characters: *H. apua* (Figs. 28-30) has a shorter, smaller and more inflated shell than *H. pukua* (Figs. 54-57); the protoconch of *H. apua* is 1.5 whorls long (Fig. 31), while that of *H. pukua* has only 1 whorl (Figs. 58-59), which is difficult to see as it is eroded in most adult specimens (Figs. 54-56); the shell aperture is shorter and wider in *H. apua* (Figs. 28-29) than in *H. pukua* (Figs. 54, 57). Anatomically, there are the following additional differences: the snout has a flap-like, slightly oblique anterior surface in *H. apua* (Fig. 44), while that of *H. pukua* is flatter and transverse (Fig. 62); the operculum of *H. pukua* is unique in being double layered (Fig. 66); *H. apua* has a simpler and shorter anterior esophagus (Fig. 44) than that of *H. pukua*, which is coiled inside haemocoel (Fig. 62: es); the penis of *H. apua* is shorter, with a wider base (Fig. 50), while the penis of *H. pukua* is ~50% longer, slender and with a more uniform width along its length (Figs. 63-64); in the pallial oviduct, *H. apua* has a zigzag

of ingesting gland, and the receptacle is bifid (Fig. 52), while in that of *H. pukua* the ingesting gland has a single loop, and the receptacle is simpler, balloon-like (Fig. 65).

The genus *Heleobia* is very diverse, with about 90 species in South America (HERSHLER & THOMPSON, 1992; CAZANIGA, 2011; COLLADO, 2015). As most species have a high degree of endemism, the comparison of both new species is focused in the species which occur in the region (SIMONE, 2006a: 88-94) and in freshwater environment, disregarding some species which only occur in brackish waters. *Heleobia apua* and *H. pukua* differ from *H. bertoniana* (Pilsbry, 1911), from Paraguay, in having a proportionally shorter shell, with less convex whorls, and a proportionally shallower suture; both differ from *H. manni* (Baker, 1913), from Northeast Brazil, and from *H. siolii* (Haas, 1949), from Pará, in having a much less obese and more elongated profile, and a proportionally smaller aperture; both differ from *H. parchapei* (d'Orbigny, 1835), from South Brazil, in having a less pointed spire, fewer whorls, with a flatter profile; both differ from *H. robusta* Silva & Veiternheimer-Mendes, 2004 in being much more elongated, and in having a proportionally smaller aperture; both differ from *Lyrodes subgranulatus* (Haas, 1952), from Pará, in having less convex whorls, and a proportionally shallower suture; both additionally differ from both *Idiopyrgus* species, from N-NE Brazil, in being much smaller, with fewer whorls, spire more obese and last whorl not fully projected from the normal shell growth.

Anatomically, the distinction of both *Heleobia* species are difficult to explore, as the anatomical information is scanty in literature, and is not as detailed as the present one. They differ from most species [e.g., *H. atacemensis* (Philippi, 1860), *H. deserticola* Collado, 2015] (SILVA, 2003; COLLADO ET AL, 2013; COLLADO, 2015) in lacking bulged glandular structures, also called stalked glands (DAVIS ET AL, 1982) on the outer edge of the penis. In fact, the smooth penis, lacking bulged structures, approaches both new species

to the genus *Andesipyrgus* Hershler & Velkovrh, 1993, in which both new species cannot belong because lacking a peristome totally detached from the penultimate whorl, a pupiliform outline, a pigmented animal, and a coiled oviduct. The simple penis appears to be linked to the subterranean cochliopid taxa (HERSHLER & VELKOVHR, 1993), which is not the case of both new species.

The anatomical features of the genital system of the three species studied here has the usual configuration of the family Cochliopidae. The bulged portion in the end region of the visceral oviduct, however, have not attracted the attention. It is called ingesting gland herein, as it does not look like a receptacle or a bursa copulatrix, and is not fully hollow. On the other hand, a seminal receptacle located close to the pallial oviduct insertion appears to be a common cochliopid feature. It is sometimes called bursa copulatrix, a structure that usually is located anteriorly, close to the female genital aperture. The insertion of the male visceral vas deferens in the prostate has also not attracted attention, but seems an interesting feature, as sometimes it is terminal, and sometimes subterminal. The same can be said of the origin of the pallial vas deferens after prostate portion.

The three new described species apparently are not widely distributed. They are possibly endemic of that region. Further studies on their distribution and local anthropic impact are necessary for confirming the degree of endemism and possible protective measures for them.

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